

Quantum chemical predictions of vibrational mode analysis of germaformaldehyde and related molecules

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Abstract : Hybrid density functional theory and *ab-initio* methods have been evaluated as practical tools for calculations of infrared vibrational frequencies and absorption intensities of XGeWZ molecules (where X = O, S, Se; W, Z = H, F, Cl). The theoretical results have been compared with the most current experimental data. It shows that XGeWZ species have two states, namely singlet (¹Σ) state and triplet (³Σ) state. We have found that the singlet (¹Σ) state of the species is more stable than the triplet (³Σ) state. When different halogens combine to the central Ge atom, the bond length order is Ge-H < Ge-F < Ge-Cl, and the energy order is HGeXH > FGeXF > ClGeXCl (where X = O, S, Se). When element X alters, the bond length order is Ge=O < Ge=S < Ge=Se, and the energy order is WGeOZ < WGeSZ < WGeSeZ. The orders of the bond angles are ∠WGeO < ∠WGeS < ∠WGeSe and ∠WGeZ (X=O) > ∠WGeZ (X=S) > ∠WGeZ (X=Se) (where W, Z = H, F, Cl). The vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode analysis are well agreeing with the optimized geometric results.

Keywords : Germaformaldehyde derivatives, vibrational frequencies, *ab-initio* methods.

A great amount of effort has been put into reproducing the molecular spectroscopy by quantum chemical calculations based on *ab-initio* methods for over the past three decades. The vibrational frequencies and the corresponding absorption intensities generated by *ab-initio* methods at the Hartree-Fock calculations compared with experiments are far from perfection. For example, the harmonic frequencies calculated by Hartree-Fock methods are in most cases 10% higher than those derived from experimental observations. IR spectra simulations require *ab-initio* techniques to get reliable intensities. However, recent *ab-initio* calculations can already provide accurate molecular geometries and frequencies. Therefore, probably these new methods can be used to simulate IR spectra, while the dipole-moment surfaces are described at high levels of theory to get satisfactory intensities. In the vibrational spectroscopy, the interest toward deriving from experimenting the potential force fields of molecules through quite complicated but still approximate semi-classical procedures is gradually fading in view of the straightforward evaluation of quite accurate force fields from *ab-initio* quantum mechanical computations.

The difficulties in assigning the numerous observed bands in a spectrum to particular vibrational modes have also been largely overcome with the aid of theoretically determined normal coordinates¹. For a number of small molecules that highly correlated wave functions employing basis sets of medium sizes can produce estimates of vibrational frequencies within an average deviation of about 1% from the experimental values². The quantitative predictions of vibrational intensities have, however, turned out particularly difficult. The quantum chemical evaluation of intensities in the infrared spectra has been discussed in a number of comprehensive studies and reviews³⁻⁶.

The impact of the levels of theory and basis sets employed on the quality of theoretical predictions for a number of ground-state properties of H₂CO was discussed in a comprehensive review⁷. At higher correlated levels of theory, IR intensity results for formaldehyde from QCISD/6-311++G (d,p) computations were discussed together with the CCSD and CCSD(T) TZ2P(2df,2pd) data mentioned earlier. It should be remembered that the experimental error in the available gas-phase IR intensities is often at least 10% and includes in most cases anharmonic

and band overlap effects. In addition, the accuracy of experimental intensities for weak bands may be poorer than that for strong bands. The present study aims at evaluating the capabilities of Density Functional Theory in quantitatively predicting several basic molecular properties, with the special emphasis on intensities in the infrared spectra for WXYZ molecules (W and X = H, F, Cl; Y = C, Si and Z = O, S). Several previous *ab-initio* studies were done on the isotopic effects, electronic states, and other properties of formaldehyde and a few related molecules⁸⁻³⁰, but this is the first time that an *ab-initio* density functional theory study of a large variety of species has covered the germaformaldehyde derivatives.

Computational methods :

Our presented quantum chemical calculations have been performed by using the GAUSSIAN 98¹⁸ software package. Full geometric optimizations of these species have been carried out at the B3LYP/6-311G level of theory. This method has been shown to produce reliable results of the geometry and vibrational frequency for WGeXZ (X = O, S, Se; W, Z = H, F, Cl) complexes when compared with other methods. It has been shown that DFT can give a proper reproduction of the experimental data for the molecular structure and vibrational IR spectrum of WGeXZ (X = O, S, Se; W, Z = H, F, Cl). The applied basis set has been the 6-311G-type Gaussian function, added with multiple sets of diffuse and polarization functions to 6-311++ (3df,3pd) basis set. This basis set has been successfully used in the studies of the properties of many complexes with a reasonable small basis set superposition error. Basis set superposition

errors (BSSE) have been calculated by applying the full Boys-Bernardi counterpoise correction scheme.

DFT has been demonstrated to be an effective method for the study of electronic structures and vibration properties of molecular complexes. All molecular geometries have been fully optimized by using 6-311G basis set at B3LYP level. At the same level of theory, the infrared spectra including vibration frequencies, vibration modes and IR intensities have been obtained via analytic second derivative methods in order to determine the nature of different stationary points. The total energy has also been calculated. The interaction energy for the WGeXZ (where X = O, S, Se; W, Z = H, F, Cl) complexes has been considered as the difference between the total energies of the complexes and the separated molecules at the infinite distance. The zero-point vibration energy (ZPE) correction and the thermal correction (TC) at 298.15 degrees centigrade calculated at the B3LYP/6-311G level have been employed. The single-point energy calculations have been done using the unrestricted coupled cluster method including single and double excitations and including perturbation estimates of the effects connected with triple excitation (CCSD (T)), which have been shown to predict energies more reliably³¹.

Results and discussion

Tables 1-3 give the geometric parameters obtained using Hartree-Fork (HF), two DFT (B3LYP, B3P86) methods and the second-order Moller-Plesset perturbational theory (MP2) with a relatively large basis set (6-311G) for XGeWZ molecules (X = O, S, Se; W, Z=H, F, Cl) at their singlet and triplet states. Tables 4-

Table 1a. Bond lengths (Å) of various species shown in Fig. 1, computed using the 6-311G basis set, when X = O

System	r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}	r_{11}	r_{12}
HF												
(¹ Σ)	1.630	1.513	1.620	1.699	1.618	2.153	1.617	1.726	1.499	1.618	2.178	1.501
HF												
(³ Σ)	1.807	1.537	1.811	1.721	1.815	2.206	1.800	1.730	1.540	1.800	2.161	1.544
B3LYP												
(¹ Σ)	1.663	1.535	1.648	1.741	1.651	2.199	1.648	1.761	1.521	1.650	2.220	1.523
B3LYP												
(³ Σ)	1.833	1.558	1.875	1.770	1.800	2.376	1.852	1.781	1.571	1.841	2.270	1.567
B3P86												
(¹ Σ)	1.657	1.529	1.639	1.731	1.644	2.176	1.640	1.752	1.516	1.643	2.197	1.518
B3P86												
(³ Σ)	1.821	1.551	1.827	1.743	2.004	2.523	1.817	1.755	1.566	1.828	2.241	1.558
MP2												
(¹ Σ)	1.660	1.537	1.636	1.745	1.645	2.113	1.643	1.774	1.521	1.648	2.130	1.527

Table 1b. Bond angles ($^{\circ}$) of various species shown in Fig. 1, computed using the 6-311G basis set, when X = O

System	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8	a_9	a_{10}	a_{11}	a_{12}
HF												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.31	113.38	128.98	102.09	126.25	107.50	132.78	122.39	104.83	130.59	122.53	106.88
HF												
($^3\Sigma$)	105.16	112.90	120.80	118.46	105.49	111.02	107.05	103.59	108.27	106.00	104.78	109.45
B3LYP												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.20	113.63	128.60	102.90	126.58	106.87	132.76	121.99	105.25	130.75	122.79	106.47
B3LYP												
($^3\Sigma$)	103.43	109.60	105.28	106.14	97.66	164.62	102.93	105.37	107.49	102.97	105.22	106.97
B3P86												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.00	114.03	128.63	102.79	126.41	107.18	132.79	121.95	105.25	130.73	122.63	106.64
B3P86												
($^3\Sigma$)	103.75	110.01	105.10	107.02	145.99	68.03	103.87	104.38	107.27	103.25	105.43	107.24
MP2												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.3	113.4	130.1	99.83	126.7	106.6	134.8	122.2	103.0	129.2	123.5	107.3

Table 2a. Bond lengths (\AA) of various species shown in Fig. 1, computed using the 6-311G basis set, when X = S

System	r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}	r_{11}	r_{12}
HF												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.069	1.513	2.055	1.705	2.058	2.168	2.050	1.729	1.505	2.054	2.191	1.505
HF												
($^3\Sigma$)	2.300	1.527	2.384	1.738	2.328	2.223	2.306	1.753	1.531	2.301	2.233	1.528
B3LYP												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.087	1.530	2.069	1.745	2.073	2.207	2.067	1.765	1.524	2.070	2.226	1.523
B3LYP												
($^3\Sigma$)	2.303	1.554	2.398	1.777	2.350	2.277	2.338	1.787	1.569	2.322	2.280	1.564
B3P86												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.072	1.526	2.050	1.736	2.054	2.183	2.051	1.756	1.518	2.055	2.203	1.518
B3P86												
($^3\Sigma$)	2.277	1.546	2.355	1.767	2.314	2.247	2.307	1.775	1.560	2.293	2.251	1.555
MP2												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.034	1.536	2.082	1.746	2.019	2.119	2.013	1.774	1.524	2.021	2.138	1.528

6 list the sum of electronic and zero-point energies relative to the two states, respectively. Tables 7–9 give the vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode assignment for all molecules in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state (at B3LYP level). Fig. 1 describes the structures and six normal vibrational modes of the molecules, and Fig. 2 shows the energies of the molecules visually. In the following subsections, discussions will be made according to the structural classification.

Geometries :

The geometric optimizations have indicated that there are two conformers for XGeWZ (X = O, S, Se; W, Z = H, F, Cl) species : the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) and triplet ($^3\Sigma$) states.

The singlet state is more stable than the triplet state and thus may be assigned to the ground state of Ge=X (X = O, S, Se) weakly bonding complexes. The singlet states are structurally planer while the triplet states are pyramidal.

We can see from Table 1a that for the ground state ($^1\Sigma$), the optimized Ge=O bond length is within 1.617–1.663 \AA at DFT theoretical levels while the largest deviation is 0.046 \AA . They are very close to the MP2 value (\sim 1.646 \AA). In Table 2a, the optimized Ge=S bond length is within 2.050–2.087 \AA with only a largest deviation of 0.037 \AA . They are slightly larger by 0.016–0.053 \AA than the MP2 value (\sim 2.034 \AA). The optimized Ge=Se bond length is within 2.137–2.194 \AA with only a

Table 2b. Bond angles ($^{\circ}$) of various species shown in Fig. 1, computed using the 6-311G basis set, when X = S

System	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8	a_9	a_{10}	a_{11}	a_{12}
HF												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.94	112.12	129.71	100.68	127.36	105.34	132.98	123.27	103.76	130.71	124.08	105.22
HF												
($^3\Sigma$)	107.18	111.08	107.21	102.21	108.25	107.27	109.15	106.62	105.23	108.29	108.34	105.91
B3LYP												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.74	112.60	128.69	102.72	127.18	105.80	132.58	122.90	104.52	130.77	123.98	105.26
B3LYP												
($^3\Sigma$)	104.95	108.35	107.06	103.13	107.36	108.43	106.28	106.26	105.34	106.18	106.60	104.37
B3P86												
($^1\Sigma$)	123.63	112.77	128.66	102.71	127.12	105.81	132.64	122.86	104.50	130.83	123.74	105.43
B3P86												
($^3\Sigma$)	105.33	108.71	106.97	103.16	107.48	108.14	106.39	106.72	105.72	106.56	106.89	104.81
MP2												
($^1\Sigma$)	124.4	111.1	130.6	98.72	127.7	104.7	135.2	123.3	101.5	130.5	124.4	105.1

Table 3a. Bond lengths (\AA) of various species shown in Fig. 1, computed using the 6-311G basis set, when X = Se

System	r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	r_7	r_8	r_9	r_{10}	r_{11}	r_{12}
HF												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.176	1.515	2.165	1.708	2.167	2.173	2.158	1.733	1.507	2.163	2.195	1.506
HF												
($^3\Sigma$)	2.383	1.503	2.578	1.743	2.453	2.228	2.376	1.742	1.542	2.414	2.239	1.529
B3LYP												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.194	1.532	2.199	1.757	2.161	2.178	2.173	1.769	1.527	2.155	2.203	1.514
B3LYP												
($^3\Sigma$)	2.411	1.555	2.527	1.779	2.739	2.338	2.452	1.789	1.570	2.434	2.285	1.564
B3P86												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.156	1.536	2.444	1.768	2.159	2.189	2.137	1.745	1.532	2.159	2.210	1.520
B3P86												
($^3\Sigma$)	2.296	1.513	2.476	1.785	2.430	2.253	2.374	1.764	1.569	2.362	2.192	1.559
MP2												
($^1\Sigma$)	2.162	1.536	2.137	1.749	2.148	2.122	2.141	1.775	1.526	2.149	2.140	1.529

largest deviation of 0.057 \AA (see Table 3a). They are slightly different from the MP2 value, too. This best agreement among the bond length results, together with the recent investigations about other weakly bound species, has implied that three DFT and MP2 methods are applicable here. For the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$), a similar tendency has also been observed. The Ge=O bond in the singlet state is significantly shorter than that of the triplet state, so are the Ge=S and Ge=Se bonds. This phenomenon has indicated that the singlet state ($^1\Sigma$) is more stable than the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$). These Ge=S bond lengths in both states are significantly longer by about 0.4 \AA than those of the Ge=O bond lengths at four theoretical levels. However, they are slightly shorter by

about 0.1 \AA than those of the Ge=Se bond lengths. So the relative bond lengths order is Ge=O < Ge=S < Ge=Se.

The optimized Ge-H bond length is 1.513–1.537 \AA , and the Ge-F bond length falls within 1.705–1.749 \AA , while the Ge-Cl bond length is 2.113–2.197 \AA at four different theoretical methods. The calculated largest deviations are only 0.025, 0.044 and 0.084 \AA , respectively. It can be seen that the relative stability order of Ge-W (where W = H, F, Cl) bonds is Ge-H > Ge-F > Ge-Cl, obviously.

From the values of Tables 1b–3b, we can see the bond angles of the molecules WGeXZ (X = O, S, Se; W,

Table 3b. Bond angles ($^{\circ}$) of various species shown in Fig. 1, computed using the 6-311G basis set, when X = Se

System	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8	a_9	a_{10}	a_{11}	a_{12}
HF												
($^1\Sigma$)	124.36	111.29	130.04	100.04	127.68	104.65	133.47	123.45	103.08	131.13	124.46	104.41
HF												
($^3\Sigma$)	117.35	125.31	106.56	100.87	108.76	106.32	110.40	105.83	105.65	109.34	108.73	105.07
B3LYP												
($^1\Sigma$)	124.21	111.65	130.11	99.17	127.63	104.50	133.57	122.78	103.65	131.32	124.55	104.78
B3LYP												
($^3\Sigma$)	105.58	107.61	107.82	102.41	107.92	170.12	107.12	106.83	104.61	107.08	106.69	103.63
B3P86												
($^1\Sigma$)	124.55	110.91	130.23	99.60	127.57	104.87	134.06	123.97	101.96	131.46	123.91	104.63
B3P86												
($^3\Sigma$)	117.64	124.72	107.83	102.88	107.66	107.40	107.94	105.53	104.66	107.95	104.98	104.90
MP2												
($^1\Sigma$)	124.6	110.9	130.7	98.62	127.8	104.4	135.2	123.4	101.4	130.5	124.8	104.8

Table 4. Sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/Particle) when X = O

System	HGeOH	FGeOF	ClGeOCl	HGeOF	HGeOCl
HF ($^1\Sigma$)	-2151.2814	-2349.0829	-3069.1775	-2250.2108	-2610.2634
HF ($^3\Sigma$)	-2151.2457	-2348.9768	-3069.1664	-2250.1717	-2610.2119
B3LYP ($^1\Sigma$)	-2153.3568	-2351.9579	-3072.6770	-2252.6641	-2613.0229
B3LYP ($^3\Sigma$)	-2153.2995	-2351.9114	-3072.6190	-2252.6034	-2612.9662
B3P86 ($^1\Sigma$)	-2154.2578	-2353.1261	-3074.1895	-2253.6967	-2614.2236
B3P86 ($^3\Sigma$)	-2154.1942	-2353.1223	-3073.9921	-2253.6726	-2614.1637

Table 5. Sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/Particle) when X = S

System	HGeSH	FGeSF	ClGeSCl	HGeSF	HGeSCl
HF ($^1\Sigma$)	-2473.9488	-2671.7875	-3391.8700	-2572.8723	-2932.9137
HF ($^3\Sigma$)	-2473.9348	-2671.7849	-3391.8668	-2572.8563	-2932.9011
B3LYP ($^1\Sigma$)	-2476.3676	-2674.9709	-3395.6875	-2575.6737	-2936.0322
B3LYP ($^3\Sigma$)	-2476.3209	-2674.9363	-3395.6548	-2575.6241	-2935.9868
B3P86 ($^1\Sigma$)	-2477.4279	-2676.3014	-3397.3553	-2576.8691	-2937.3963
B3P86 ($^3\Sigma$)	-2477.3792	-2676.2632	-3397.3184	-2576.8168	-2937.3480

Table 6. Sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/Particle) when X = Se

System	HGeSeH	FGeSeF	ClGeSeCl	HGeSeF	HGeSeCl
HF ($^1\Sigma$)	-4476.2221	-4674.0624	-5394.1449	-4575.1840	-4935.1876
HF ($^3\Sigma$)	-4476.1899	-4674.0612	-5394.1426	-4575.1456	-4935.1756
B3LYP ($^1\Sigma$)	-4479.7032	-4678.2768	-5399.0072	-4579.0094	-4939.3889
B3LYP ($^3\Sigma$)	-4479.6592	-4678.2692	-5398.9879	-4578.9629	-4939.3262
B3P86 ($^1\Sigma$)	-4481.2979	-4680.0855	-5401.1739	-4580.7467	-4941.2338
B3P86 ($^3\Sigma$)	-4477.0276	-4680.0762	-5401.1410	-4580.6942	-4941.2138

Z = H, F, Cl). For the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$), there are obvious changes compared with the ground state ($^1\Sigma$). For the ground state ($^1\Sigma$), the data have shown that the key angles $\angle WGeX$ (W = H, F, Cl; X = O, S, Se) are about 122–

133 $^{\circ}$ at three DFT and MP2 levels with 6-311G basis set which are significantly larger by 10–23 $^{\circ}$ than that (103–111 $^{\circ}$) in the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$). The optimized $\angle FGeF$ and $\angle ClGeCl$ angles are about 102.6 $^{\circ}$ and 107.0 $^{\circ}$ in the singlet

Table 7. Vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) and vibrational mode assignment for the WGeOZ (W, Z = H, F, Cl) molecules in the singlet (¹Σ) state at B3LYP level

Species	Freq.	Assignment	Species	Freq.	Assignment
HGeOH	569.7	H ¹ GeH ² rock out of plane	FGeOF	186.6	F ¹ GeOF ² rock out of plane
	601.5	H ¹ GeH ² rock in plane		234.3	F ¹ GeOF ² rock in plane
	909.2	H ¹ GeH ² bend		245.8	F ¹ GeF ² bend
	920.6	GeO stretch		670.1	F ¹ GeF ² stretch
	2086.9	H ¹ GeH ² stretch		703.4	F ¹ GeF ² as-stretch
	2101.9	H ¹ GeH ² as-stretch		939.4	GeO stretch
ClGeOCl	147.4	Cl ¹ GeCl ² bend	HGeOF	250.2	FGeO bend
	154.6	Cl ¹ GeOCl ² rock out of plane		432.8	GeH rock out of plane
		Cl ¹ GeOCl ² rock in plane		666.6	GeF stretch
	195.7	Cl ¹ GeCl ² stretch		762.9	GeH rock in plane
	359.9	Cl ¹ GeCl ² as-stretch		943.9	GeO stretch
	397.2	GeO stretch		2162.0	GeH stretch
	925.1				
HGeOCl	204.1	ClGeO bend			
	368.5	GeH rock out of plane			
	374.6	GeCl stretch			
	761.0	GeH rock in plane			
	940.1	GeO stretch			
	2169.2	GeH stretch			

Table 8. Vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) and vibrational mode assignment for the WGeSZ (W, Z = H, F, Cl) molecules in the singlet (¹Σ) state at B3LYP level

Species	Freq.	Assignment	Species	Freq.	Assignment
HGeSH	507.1	GeS stretch	FGeSF	141.4	F ¹ GeSF ² rock out of plane
	520.6	H ¹ GeH ² rock out of plane		173.3	F ¹ GeSF ² rock in plane
	564.1	H ¹ GeH ² rock in plane		243	F ¹ GeF ² bend
	919.7	H ¹ GeH ² bend		475.5	GeS stretch
	2145.2	H ¹ GeH ² stretch		700.6	GeF ¹ stretch
	2159.3	H ¹ GeH ² as-stretch		700.8	GeF ² stretch
ClGeSCl	117.5	Cl ¹ GeSCl ² rock out of plane	HGeSF	198.6	FGeS bend
	137.3	Cl ¹ GeSCl ² rock in plane		368.2	GeH rock out of plane
	149.0	Cl ¹ GeCl ² bend		507.2	GeS stretch
	344.7	Cl ¹ GeCl ² stretch		669.5	GeF stretch
	391.0	Cl ¹ GeCl ² as-stretch		774.1	GeH rock in plane
	516.6	GeS stretch		2179.1	GeH stretch
HGeSCl	146.3	ClGeS bend			
	361.7	GeCl stretch			
	368.1	GeH rock out of plane			
	516.0	GeS stretch			
	700.6	GeH rock in plane			
	2185.9	GeH stretch			

(¹Σ) state of WGeOZ (W, Z = H, F, Cl) species, a little smaller by about 1–2° than those in the triplet state (³Σ). And the angles ∠HGeF and ∠HGeCl are also a little

smaller by 1–2° in the singlet (¹Σ) state than those in the triplet state (³Σ). Interestingly, the angle ∠HGeH in the singlet (¹Σ) state is about 113.6° which is a little larger

Table 9. Vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) and vibrational mode assignment for the WGeSeZ ($\text{W, Z} = \text{H, F, Cl}$) molecules in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state at B3LYP level

Species	Freq.	Assignment	Species	Freq.	Assignment
HGeSeH	362.0	GeSe stretch	FGeSeF	86.1	F^1GeF^2 bend
	492.1	H^1GeH^2 rock out of plane		101.1	F^1GeF^2 rock out of plane
	516.3	H^1GeH^2 rock in plane		159.0	F^1GeF^2 rock in plane
	899.5	H^1GeH^2 bend		265.3	GeSe stretch
	2098.6	H^1GeH^2 stretch		579.4	GeF^1 stretch
	2110.5	H^1GeH^2 as-stretch		624.5	GeF^2 stretch
ClGeSeCl	59.0	Cl^1GeCl^2 rock out of plane	HGeSeF	167.8	FGeSe bend
	62.9	Cl^1GeCl^2 bend		362.6	GeSe stretch
	118.5	Cl^1GeCl^2 rock in plane		379.8	GeH rock out of plane
	248.2	GeSe stretch		646.6	GeF stretch
	327.1	Cl^1GeCl^2 stretch		757.8	GeH rock in plane
	346.9	Cl^1GeCl^2 as-stretch		2138.1	GeH stretch
HGeSeCl	108.7	ClGeSe bend			
	250.3	GeSe stretch			
	271.7	GeH rock out of plane			
	332.4	GeCl stretch			
	588.2	GeH rock in plane			
	2238.0	GeH stretch			

by about 3° than that (110.8°) in the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$). The results in the WGeSZ and WGeSeZ ($\text{W, Z} = \text{H, F, Cl}$) species are the same.

As we can see from Tables 1b–3b, the angles $\angle\text{HGeO}$ are 123.31 , 123.20 and 123.00° in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state at three DFT levels, so they inosculate with the result at MP2 level (123.30°) best. The angles $\angle\text{HGeS}$ are 123.94 , 123.74 , 123.63 and 124.4° at three DFT and MP2 levels at 6-311G basis set, and the $\angle\text{HGeSe}$ are 124.36 , 124.21 , 124.55 and 124.6° . So the relative angles order is $\angle\text{HGeO} < \angle\text{HGeS} < \angle\text{HGeSe}$. We can conclude that the order of the angles $\angle\text{FGeX}$ and $\angle\text{ClGeX}$ ($\text{X} = \text{O, S, Se}$) are the same from the Tables 1b–3b at the same time. They are $\angle\text{FGeO} < \angle\text{FGeS} < \angle\text{FGeSe}$ and $\angle\text{ClGeO} < \angle\text{ClGeS} < \angle\text{ClGeSe}$. But as we can see, the angles $\angle\text{HGeH}$ are 113.38 , 113.63 , 114.03 and 113.4° at the three DFT and MP2 levels when $\text{X}=\text{O}$, and they are 112.12 , 112.60 , 112.77 and 111.1° when $\text{X}=\text{S}$, and 111.29 , 111.65 , 110.91 and 110.9° when $\text{X}=\text{Se}$. So the order of angles $\angle\text{HGeH}$ in the three different species is $\angle\text{HGeH} (\text{X}=\text{O}) > \angle\text{HGeH} (\text{X}=\text{S}) > \angle\text{HGeH} (\text{X}=\text{Se})$. The angles $\angle\text{HGeF}$ and $\angle\text{HGeCl}$ have the same order, namely they are $\angle\text{HGeF} (\text{X}=\text{O}) > \angle\text{HGeF} (\text{X}=\text{S}) > \angle\text{HGeF} (\text{X}=\text{Se})$ and $\angle\text{HGeCl} (\text{X}=\text{O}) > \angle\text{HGeCl} (\text{X}=\text{S}) > \angle\text{HGeCl} (\text{X}=\text{Se})$. But they only have a little difference in data. Obviously all these considerable structural

differences among the three species should be attributed to the bonding differences among them.

Energies :

Interaction energies are calculated by taking the energy difference between the complexes, which are listed in Tables 4–6. We also describe the energies of the molecules in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state at B3LYP level in Fig. 2. To correct the basis set superposition error (BSSE), the counterpoise (CP) method is employed. Zero-point energy (ZPVE) corrections are applied at the same time.

In details, the results in Tables 4–6 indicate that the energies of the singlet state ($^1\Sigma$) are significantly lower than the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$), and the calculated state-state adiabatic energy separations between these two states are within 0.01 – 0.07 Hartree/Particle at several different theoretical levels. Three HF and DFT methods (B3LYP and B3P86) give good agreement results (0.0111 – 0.0636 Hartree/Particle) with a small deviation of ~ 0.0525 Hartree/Particle.

As expected, method sensitivity exists. The interaction energy computed with HF is much higher. The general importance including zero-point energy (ZPVE) corrections in calculating binding energies has been well documented in the literature³². In Table 6, we can see that the energies of HGeOH molecule are about -2151.2 ,

Fig. 1. Five structures and six normal vibrational modes of germaformaldehyde and related systems.

-2153.3 and -2154.2 Hartree/Particle at the three DFT levels. They are -2349.0, -2351.9, -2353.1 Hartree/Particle and -3069.2, -3072.6, -3074.1 Hartree/Particle of molecules FGeOF and ClGeOCl. Obviously the energy order is HGeOH > FGeOF > ClGeOCl, and the relative stability order of the three complexes is HGeOH < FGeOF < ClGeOCl, breadthwise. Meanwhile, the relative stability orders of WGeXW (W = H, F, Cl; X = S, Se) are HGeSH < FGeSF < ClGeSCl and HGeSeH < FGeSeF < ClGeSeCl, respectively. Also we can see from the Table that the energy of HGeSH is about -2476 Hartree/Particle, significantly lower by 323 Hartree/

Particle than that of HGeOH molecule, while it is much higher by about 2300 Hartree/Particle than that of HGeSeH (-4777 Hartree/Particle). So the relative stability order of HGeXH (X = O, S, Se) is HGeOH < HGeSH < HGeSeH, lengthways. The orders are the same with WGeXZ (W, Z = H, F, Cl; X = O, S, Se) molecules, namely they are FGeOF < FGeSF < FGeSeF, ClGeOCl < ClGeSCl < ClGeSeCl, HGeOF < HGeSF < HGeSeF and HGeOCl < HGeSCl < HGeSeCl, respectively. We can see this disciplinarian in Fig. 2 distinctly. So when O atom is replaced by S or Se atoms, the stability of the structures will be stronger and stronger. At the same time,

Fig. 2. Sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/Particle) of the molecules in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state at B3LYP level.

when H atom is replaced by F or Cl atoms, the structure stability will also be stronger and stronger.

Vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode analysis :

Vibrational spectroscopy is one of the most useful experimental tools for study of the bonds, so the information on calculated harmonic vibrational frequencies can be useful. As we all know that, if n is the atom number, for nonlinear molecules there are $(3n-6)$ normal vibration modes and for linear molecules there are $(3n-5)$, so the molecules $WGeXW$ ($W = H, F, Cl; X = O, S, Se$) are all have seven vibrational modes. In a sense, the numerical values of the frequencies of a molecule can reflect the activation energy. If a bond is extended or weakened, the frequencies are red-shifted while on the contrary, if the bond is shortened or strengthened, the frequencies are blue-shifted³³. So the changes of the vibrational modes must be relative to the structure stability. Vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode assignment for all molecules in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state at B3LYP level are listed in Tables 7-9.

As we can see from the Tables, for $WGeXW$ ($W = H, F, Cl; X = O, S, Se$) molecules, there are five $WGeW$ vibrational modes : rock out of plane, out in plane, stretch, as-stretch, bend, and one GeX vibrational mode : stretch. There are also six vibrational modes for $HGeXW$ (where $W = F, Cl; X = O, S, Se$) molecules : $WGeX$ scissors, GeH rock out of plane, rock in plane and stretch, GeW stretch and GeX stretch. We have found that the $Ge-X$ stretchings in $HGeXH$ ($X = O, S, Se$) are 920.6 ($X = O$), 507.1 ($X = S$) and 362.0 cm^{-1} ($X = Se$), significantly smaller and smaller. They are $943.9, 507.2, 362.6$ cm^{-1} and $940.1, 516.0, 250.3$ cm^{-1} of $HGeXF$ and $HGeXCl$ species, respectively, having the same orders as $HGeXH$ species, and the $FGeXF$ and $ClGeXCl$ species are the same, too. Thus when S or Se atoms substitute the O atom, the $Ge=X$ ($X = O, S, Se$) vibrations will be weaker and weaker, namely the bond strength is weaker and weaker. They are inosulating with the bond length result $Ge=O < Ge=S < Ge=Se$ and the bond angle order $\angle WGeO < \angle WGeS < \angle WGeSe$ ideally.

In $HGeOZ$ species, when Z alters ($H \rightarrow F \rightarrow Cl$), the $Ge-H$ stretch mode is blue-shifted from ~ 2094 cm^{-1} to 2162.0 and 2169.2 cm^{-1} , breadthwise. Furthermore, it is blue-shifted from ~ 2152 cm^{-1} to 2179.1 and 2185.9 cm^{-1} in $HGeSZ$ species, and from ~ 2104 cm^{-1} to 2138.1 and 2238.0 cm^{-1} in $HGeSeZ$ species. Obviously, the change of Z atom strengthens the $Ge-H$ stretching, and the $Ge-H$ bond is more stable. In addition, in $WGeOW$ ($W = H,$

F, Cl) molecules, the $FGeF$ bending (245.8 cm^{-1}) is much smaller than $HGeH$ bending (909.2 cm^{-1}), but significantly larger than $ClGeCl$ bending (147.4 cm^{-1}). They are $919.7, 243.0, 149.0$ cm^{-1} and $899.5, 86.1, 62.9$ cm^{-1} in $WGeSW$ and $WGeSeW$ ($W = H, F, Cl$) species, respectively, having been smaller and smaller, obviously. These results indicated that in the change of $HGeH \rightarrow FGeF \rightarrow ClGeCl$, the vibrational intensity is degenerating. It is noticeable that there are more degenerating vibrational modes, as the Tables have shown, such as in $HGeOW$ ($W = H, F, Cl$) species, the GeH stretching is 2086.9 cm^{-1} , and the GeF stretching is 666.6 cm^{-1} , while the $GeCl$ stretching is 374.6 cm^{-1} . In $HGeSW$ ($W = H, F, Cl$) species, the three stretches are $2145.2, 669.5$ and 361.7 cm^{-1} . In $HGeSW$ ($W = H, F, Cl$) species, they are $2098.6, 646.6$ and 332.4 cm^{-1} . These results make the $Ge-W$ bond length order as $Ge-H < Ge-F < Ge-Cl$.

There are also obvious increases in the frequencies of the stretching vibration in some species, as the Tables have shown. Such as GeH stretchings, they are $2086.9, 2162.0$ and 2169.2 cm^{-1} in $HGeOH, HGeOF$ and $HGeOCl$ molecules. In $HGeSH, HGeSF$ and $HGeSCl$, they are $2145.2, 2179.1$ and 2185.9 cm^{-1} , respectively. And in $HGeSeH, HGeSeF$ and $HGeSeCl$, they are $2098.6, 2138.1$ and 2238.0 cm^{-1} , respectively. So the change of $O \rightarrow S \rightarrow Se$ makes $Ge-H$ stretch mode blue-shifted, thus the $Ge-H$ bond is strengthened, and the molecules are more and more stable, accordingly.

Conclusions :

The geometries and energies of the $XGeWZ$ molecules ($X = O, S, Se; W, Z = H, F, Cl$) have been presented in this work. The stable structures have been considered. The structures of all molecules in the singlet ($^1\Sigma$) state are more stable at all levels than those in the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$). They are structurally planer while the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) states are pyramidal. At the same time, the energies of the singlet state ($^1\Sigma$) are significantly lower than those of the triplet state ($^3\Sigma$). The bond length orders are $Ge=O < Ge=S < Ge=Se$ and $Ge-H < Ge-F < Ge-Cl$. The orders of the bond angles are $\angle WGeO < \angle WGeS < \angle WGeSe$ and $\angle WGeZ$ ($X=O$) $> \angle WGeZ$ ($X=S$) $> \angle WGeZ$ ($X=Se$) ($W, Z = H, F, Cl$). The energy orders are $HGeXH > FGeXF > ClGeXCl$ ($X = O, S, Se$) and $WGeOZ < WGeSZ < WGeSeZ$ ($W, Z = H, F, Cl$). Moreover, the IR intensities, vibrational frequencies and vibrational modes have been analyzed. We have found that when X changes ($O \rightarrow S \rightarrow Se$), the GeX stretches are significantly degenerate, and it makes $Ge-H$ stretch mode blue-shifted thus the $Ge-H$ bond is strengthened, so the

molecules are more and more stable, accordingly. When atom W alters (H→F→Cl), the WGeW bends and the GeW stretches are significantly degenerated too, but obviously, the GeH stretches are blue-shifted. All the results have indicated that the bond lengths, the bond angles and the energy orders are reliable, and the vibrational mode analysis has suggested that the mechanism is reliable, too.

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